

ENHANCING STUDENTS' COGNITIVE LEARNING OUTCOMES AND MOTIVATION THROUGH QUIZZ-BASED TEAMS-GAMES-TOURNAMENT

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the effects of Quizizz-based Teams-Games-Tournament on the cognitive learning outcomes and motivation of science 8 students in a public school in Bukidnon, Philippines. This study employed an explanatory sequential mixed-method design. The quantitative phase involved two groups exposed to the Quizizz-based Teams-Games-Tournament (QTGT) and a non-QTGT approach. For the qualitative phase, data were collected through a focus group discussion (FGD). The ANCOVA results revealed a significant difference in students' learning outcomes ($p = 0.000$, $p < .05$). However, the mean scores for both QTGT and non-QTGT groups remained below the expected level, indicating that while QTGT improves learning outcomes, its effect is not substantial enough to significantly enhance students' cognitive learning outcomes. Additionally, the ANCOVA results revealed a significant effect of the intervention on students' motivation, $F=17.870$, ($p < 0.001$). The QTGT group demonstrated higher motivation, with a mean score of 3.63 (highly motivated), compared to the non-QTGT group's mean score of 3.23 (moderately motivated). The interactive, competitive, and collaborative approach of the intervention played an important role in enhancing students' motivation in learning science. Qualitative analysis revealed five themes: (1) Perceived Understanding of the Lesson, (2) Barriers to Effective Learning and Retention, (3) Team Dynamics and Peer Influence, (4) Technology-Enhanced Learning and Accessibility, and (5) The Role of Competition in Enhancing Students' Motivation. These themes provided insights into

students' experiences, highlighting the factors that may have influenced their learning outcomes and motivation.

Keywords: *Cognitive Learning Outcomes, Collaborative Learning, Motivation, Gamification, Quizizz-based Teams-Games-Tournament*

INTRODUCTION

Science education is essential for equipping learners with the knowledge and skills to understand the world, make informed decisions, and contribute to technological advancements. The integration of technology has significantly transformed learning, especially in difficult subjects like science. Gamified and technology-enhanced approaches not only improve engagement but also support deeper comprehension of challenging topics. However, despite these innovations, many students still struggle to understand scientific concepts and retain information while maintaining motivation during difficult tasks.

These difficulties are evident in the Philippines, as indicated in the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) results. The Philippines continues to be one of the nations with poor performance in science, and nearly no students attained outstanding performance in science in the 2022 results, which were comparable to the results from 2018. The effects of the school closures caused by the pandemic also worsened this, contributing to a concerning rise in learning poverty and learning loss globally (Azevedo, 2020; Moscoviz & Evans, 2022). The National Achievement Test in SY 2017-2018 with participating Schools from the City Divisions of the Province of Bukidnon also showed that learners' performance in elementary and secondary education was unsatisfactory, falling below the national standard of 75%, reflecting limited competency in knowledge acquisition, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills according to (Añar & Manlagaylay, 2023). A similar result was observed in the study locale, as reflected in the 2019 NAT results, which showed a mean percentage score of 32.26%.

The poor level of scientific literacy among Filipino students can be attributed to various unaddressed variables. Sadera et al. (2020) stated that students have been experiencing challenges in learning science, such as difficulties affecting motivation, thinking skills, lesson material, and the learning environment. As additionally emphasized by Dagdag et al. (2019), 9 out of 23 percent of students struggle academically and in non-academic areas due to poor classroom management and pedagogy, and the lack of activities that promote students' overall development and effective learning practices. Despite the different strategies and approaches to teaching, Filipino students still face issues such as low concept retention, poor analytical and reasoning abilities, and a lack of interpersonal skills (Mempin, 2024). Therefore, education stakeholders need to engage in long-term visionary goals to help students acquire the 21st-century skills set by the Department of Education (Alinsunurin, 2021; Añar & Manlagaylay, 2023).

The use of Quizizz-based Teams-Games-Tournament (QTGT) in teaching and learning science is an innovative practice that aims to address the aforementioned challenges. Quizizz is integrated with the teams-games tournament (TGT), a form of cooperative learning where students are grouped in teams to compete in games, which can make learning fun and motivating for the students. Students engage in group discussions and collaborations, examining and learning the lessons in teams (Kharbach, 2024; Matitaputty et al., 2023). Research studies support using this approach, as it has positively impacted learning. Ekaputra (2023) claims that implementing the Quizizz application with Teams-Games-Tournament increased students' learning independence. This finding implies that the capacity of learners to perform tasks autonomously can be effectively improved by integrating Quizizz with a Teams-Games-Tournament learning model.

In addition, local studies indicate that implementing team-based learning could improve students' participation in learning science. As stated by Clementiir and Azuelo (2023), students who had experienced team-based learning demonstrated an improvement in knowledge of cognition and showed a considerable understanding of their thinking processes, which supports the idea of integrating team-based learning into science education.

The study of Tinambunan and Orongan (2023) also recommends using GBL, which increases academic achievement and enhances motivation in learning science. To supplement this, the study of Sipin and Tan (2023) revealed that students who experienced Computer-based Gamification Strategy (CGS) performed better than students who experienced non-CGS. The students had very low performance before the intervention and progressed to moderate performance after exposure to CGS.

Recognizing the need for innovative instructional methods, this study employs QTGT to improve the cognitive learning outcomes and motivation of Grade 8 students in Earth Science. By promoting collaboration, competition, and active participation, this approach aims to cultivate a classroom environment that not only motivates students but also enhances their learning outcomes.

Research Questions

1. Is there a significant difference in students' cognitive learning outcomes when exposed to Quizizz-based Teams-Games-Tournament and those exposed to non-Quizizz-based Teams-Games-Tournament?
2. Is there a significant difference between students' motivation before and after exposure to Quizizz-based Teams-Games-Tournament?
3. What are students' experiences after exposure to the Quizizz-based Teams-Games-Tournament (QTGT) in relation to their cognitive learning outcomes?
4. What are students' experiences after exposure to the Quizizz-based Teams Games-Tournament (QTGT) in relation to their motivation in learning science?

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in a public school in Bukidnon, located in the southern part of the Philippines. The school is accessible, and diverse students come from neighboring municipalities and barangays with diverse socioeconomic and cultural backgrounds. Students in the study locale are familiar with using technologies, and they can navigate different platforms and applications with ease. The study focused only on the effects of Quizizz-based teams-games-tournaments on students' cognitive learning outcomes and motivation in science 8 in the selected class of junior high school students. The study was implemented in the second quarter of the academic year 2024-2025. The scope of the lessons is based on the K-12 science curriculum including earthquakes and understanding typhoons.

Furthermore, this study used an explanatory sequential mixed-method design. It involved gathering and analyzing quantitative data in the first phase, followed by collecting and interpreting qualitative data in the second phase. The quantitative data utilized a quasi-experimental design using a researcher-made 50-item test questionnaire. The reliability test indicated a Cronbach's alpha of 0.86 indicating that the instrument used was reliable. In addition, the Students' Motivation Towards Science Learning (SMTSL) survey questionnaire adopted from Tuan et al. (2005) was used to determine motivation with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.87. The focus-group discussion was conducted to gather qualitative data from the selected participants in the experimental group through in-person interviews using semi-structured interview questions.

The participants of the interview were purposefully selected from the experimental group. Two (2) students with the highest mean difference score in the pre and posttest, and two with the highest mean difference in the SMTSL Questionnaire, Two (2) students with the same mean scores in the pre and posttest, and two with the same mean scores in the SMTSL Questionnaire, and two (2) students with the lowest mean difference score in the pre and posttest, and two (2) students with the lowest mean difference in the SMTSL Questionnaire.

Descriptive statistics were employed to gain an in-depth analysis of the cognitive retention and level of students' motivation, such as finding the frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation. Furthermore, the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to determine the significant difference before and after exposure to QTGT and non-QTGT. The qualitative data were analyzed using thematic analysis. The data was examined and organized to produce themes that provided a comprehensive description of the data. Specifically, the researcher adhered to the procedure outlined by Braun & Clarke (2012). It includes data familiarization, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining themes, and lastly, writing a report.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on Students' Cognitive Learning Outcomes

Table 1 presents the results of an ANCOVA analyzing students' post-test scores for the QTGT and non-QTGT groups. The results show that the QTGT group had a mean post-test score of 29.19 (SD = 9.70), while the non-QTGT group scored higher, with a mean of 32.94 (SD = 11.21). The group factor was statistically significant, with an F-value of 11.80 ($p < 0.001$).

Table 1. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) for Students' Cognitive Learning Outcomes in the Post Test

Group	N	Mean	SD
QTGT	32	29.1875	9.70347
Non-QTGT	32	32.9375	11.21041
Total	64	31.0625	10.57081

Source	SS	df	MS	F-value	Sig.
Model	62492.008 ^a	3	20830.669	201.694	.000
PREPER	514.758	1	514.758	4.984	.029
GROUP	2437.463	2	1218.732	11.800	.000
Error	6299.992	61	103.279		
Total	68792.000	64			

The results indicate that both the QTGT and Non-QTGT groups showed significant improvement from pretest to posttest, as reflected in the statistically significant results for the pretest scores ($p = .029$) and the group factor ($p = .000$). The non-QTGT group had a higher posttest mean score compared to the QTGT group, suggesting that students in the non-QTGT group performed slightly better. Thus, the null hypothesis that states there is no significant difference in cognitive learning outcomes between students exposed to the QTGT and those exposed to non-QTGT is rejected. However, despite this improvement, both groups still had overall scores below the "Did Not Meet Expectation" (DNME) level.

This indicates that while the Quizizz-Based Team Games Tournament (QTGT) had a positive effect on learning outcomes, its impact was not strong enough to help students improve their learning outcomes. Similarly, the non-QTGT group, which was exposed to the traditional learning method, also did not obtain a significant increase beyond the DNME level. These findings indicate the need for further instructional enhancements to improve students' cognitive learning outcomes more effectively.

In light of the findings, the results correspond with the study of Armejin and Caro (2020), which indicated that students who were exposed to game-based instruction using extrinsic reward in science had a mean score of 68.90, falling below the did not meet expectation level.

In contrast, the results from the study of Riyanti et al. (2024) demonstrated significant improvements in students' learning outcomes and motivation following the implementation of the Team Games Tournament (TGT) model. This method led to increased academic performance and higher motivation scores, emphasizing the effectiveness of this approach in enhancing cognitive development and student engagement. Moreover, to further improve physics problem-solving skills, Rachmawati et al. (2022) suggest that innovative learning models, such as the Quizizz-based Teams-Games-Tournaments method, can be a valuable tool.

Additionally, Clementiir and Azuelo (2023) found that students who participated in team-based learning exhibited enhanced cognitive understanding and greater self-awareness of their thinking processes, supporting the integration of team-based learning in science education. These findings highlight the importance of adopting active, innovative teaching strategies like TGT to foster student engagement and cognitive growth.

B. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on Students' Motivation

Table 3 presents the results of the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of students' motivation for the QTGT and non-QTGT groups. The ANCOVA results indicate that the QTGT group had a mean motivation score of 3.63 (SD = 0.49), while the non-QTGT group scored 3.23 (SD = 0.66). The overall mean score for both groups was 3.43 (SD = 0.61). The ANCOVA analysis reveals a significant effect of the intervention, wherein the f-value is 17.870 ($p < 0.001$).

Table 3. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) for Students' Motivation in the Post-Test

Group	N	Mean	SD
QTGT	32	3.6314	.49001
Non-QTGT	32	3.2306	.66197
Total	64	3.4310	.61202

Source	SS	df	MS	F-value	Sig.
Model	761.319 ^a	3	253.773	988.092	.000
PREPER	5.361	1	5.361	20.874	.000
Group	9.179	2	4.590	17.870	.000
Error	15.667	61	.257		
Total	776.986	64			

Legend: 4.51 - 5.00 Very High Motivation (VHM); 3.51 - 4.50 High Motivation (HM); 2.51 - 3.50 Moderate Motivation (MM); 1.51 - 2.50 Low Motivation (LM); 1.00 - 1.50 Very Low Motivation (VLM)

The results demonstrate that the QTGT group exhibited a higher mean motivation level compared to the non-QTGT group after the intervention. The significant F-value for the group factor indicates that the intervention had a substantial impact on students' motivation.

The data suggest that the QTGT approach was more effective in enhancing students' motivation compared to non-QTGT. Therefore, the null hypothesis that states there is no significant difference in students' motivation before and after exposure to QTGT is rejected.

The result is consistent with the research findings of Khan et al. (2017) which emphasized the benefits of digital game-based learning (GBL) and gamification in fostering student engagement and learning outcomes. Additionally, Tinambunan and Orongan (2023) revealed that students exposed to game-based learning (GBL) showed higher motivation, which in turn positively influences their academic performance. Similarly, Capinding (2022) demonstrated the positive impact of Quizizz on students' motivation, interest, and achievement in physics, suggesting that Quizizz as an instructional tool that effectively enhances student engagement.

C. Students' Experiences after Exposure to (QTGT) in Relation to their Cognitive Learning Outcomes

Theme 1. Perceived Understanding of the Lesson

This theme highlights students' perceived understanding of the lesson. Before the lesson, many students admitted that they had little to no prior knowledge about earthquakes and typhoons which confirms with their pretest scores. They were unfamiliar with the concepts as to why earthquakes occur and the factors contributing to typhoon formation. However, after the lessons were discussed and the activities, they mentioned that they were able to learn and understand the topics.

Several students shared that they understood the lesson more clearly. Accordingly, *"Before this lesson, I had no idea what happens during an earthquake. But after you taught us, I quickly learned the terms, where earthquakes start, and why they happen."* Another student mentioned, *"I also learned that tsunamis can be caused by earthquakes, especially along reverse faults. That lesson helped me understand, and I won't forget it because it's important."*

Students also developed a better understanding of typhoons. One student shared, *"Now I know that typhoons form when the ocean surface temperature rises above 26.5°C,"* while another added, *"I used to think typhoons just appeared out of nowhere, but now I understand they are caused by warm ocean waters as well."* These responses highlight how the lesson clarified their misconceptions.

Additionally, a student emphasized the value of interactive discussions, stating, *"I really like it when you explain because it helps us understand better."* This suggests that the classroom discussions played an important role in enhancing student learning, which also aligns with the improvement observed in the non-QTGT group that was exposed to the traditional class discussions.

Moreover, the students acknowledged that repeated exposure and practice contributed to their increased familiarity with the topic. Initially, they struggled with certain

concepts, but as they attended more classes and participated in discussions, they became more confident in their understanding. One student stated, *"At first, I wasn't very familiar with the topic, but after several classes, I finally understood it."* Another student highlighted the importance of experiential learning, saying, *"It was even more exciting when we got to act out the earthquake drill and practice what to do, like duck, cover, and hold."* This suggests that hands-on activities reinforced their learning, and they were able to apply the concepts in real-life situations.

The findings of Shafqat and Habib (2022) support the positive impact of team-based learning (TBL) on both student motivation and academic performance. Their study demonstrated a significant improvement in students' performance and motivation before and after the intervention, establishing a clear connection between these factors. This aligns with the research of Clementiir and Azuelo (2023), who also found that TBL enhances academic achievement. Furthermore, Chen et al. (2015) noted that game-based learning, particularly when combined with collaborative efforts, improves problem-solving skills and contributes to a deeper understanding of the topic. Collectively, these studies emphasize the effectiveness of team-based and game-based learning strategies in improving student engagement, motivation, and academic performance.

Theme 2. Barriers to Effective Learning and Retention

While students have reported an improvement in their prior knowledge, their cognitive learning outcomes were below 75%, indicating a limited understanding of the lesson. This theme reveals various factors that hinder students' ability to effectively learn and retain information based on their experiences. These barriers include absenteeism, which causes students to miss classes and disrupts continuity in learning. Poor learning habits, such as a lack of study routines and minimal effort in reviewing the lessons, student behavior, and classroom distractions such as not paying attention during discussions, passive participation, and excessive use of mobile phones which negatively impact engagement and focus. Another significant factor is the lack of comprehension in using English, which affects students' ability to fully grasp lesson content, and the English language used during exams, particularly in subjects that rely on technical explanations. These factors may be the reason behind the low learning outcomes and retention of concepts.

One of the factors is absenteeism. When they were asked about the factors that affect their low scores in the exam, a student stated, *"misunderstanding, because I was left behind on the topic and couldn't catch up, that's why I didn't understand, I ended up making mistakes, and I was also absent at times."* This indicates that regular attendance is important because when students miss lessons, they fall behind and have a hard time catching up.

More so, some students admitted that they didn't make time to review their lessons, stating, *"I didn't study,"* indicating a lack of preparation for tests. Others expressed a lack of interest in studying, *"I feel lazy to study,"* which suggests that their engagement with learning is minimal. Additionally, the use of cellphones contributes to this issue, as one student mentioned, *"We prioritize our phones more than studying,"*

ma'am, so we end up forgetting the lessons," while another student said, *"I'm busy"*. However, some students stated, *"we study during our vacant time,"* implying that while studying is not a consistent priority, they only study during vacant times. These statements emphasize the need for strategies to enhance learning habits to improve learning outcomes.

Many students mentioned that they lost focus during lessons. Some got distracted by chatting with classmates instead of listening, *"Our score decreased because sometimes during class discussions, I would get carried away joking around with my classmates, which led to misunderstandings...."* Others admitted, *"I am not paying attention to the class discussion....,"* showing that they struggled to stay focused.

Another big challenge for some students was understanding English because English is used in exams. *"I did not study, and I find it hard to understand English."* This shows that some students struggled to understand the content simply because of the language used in lessons and exams.

The results show that the low cognitive learning outcomes of students are not just about how the lessons are taught, they are also affected by their habits and behaviors. Skipping classes, not reviewing, getting distracted, and struggling with English all play a role in why they find it hard to remember and understand lessons.

The above findings connect with the study of Ancheta et al. (2021), who found a relationship between absenteeism and student performance, with frequent absences correlated with lower scores. According to the data presented by Cepada and Grepon (2020), students in a public school in Northern Bukidnon had committed absences ranging from 15 to 55 days, and 7% of the students were absent for 55 days. Their findings indicate that absenteeism was prevalent among the respondents. In addition, Elis (2016) discovered that low exam performance is caused by frequent absences, with an overall mean score of 1.13, which is considered unsatisfactory.

Furthermore, although using mobile phones has benefits, particularly in education, excessive use of such technology can result in addiction and potentially disrupt focus. Bulawan et al. (2023) found that students often spend significant time on social media and online games, which hinders learning and diverts attention. This underscores the importance of teachers monitoring and limiting cell phone use, especially during class hours.

Moreover, it has been observed that students are practicing poor learning habits, which have been linked to lower scores in exams and difficulties retaining information. Similar findings have been reported by Salcedo-Relucio (2019), who showed a positive correlation between students' study habits and grades, which implied that insufficient study time results in poor academic performance. Furthermore, students need to enhance their learning strategies, as these play a crucial role in achieving better learning outcomes. Some students do not prioritize studying and tend to focus on other activities. As Ercan et al. (2016) noted, effective learning strategies contribute to improved learning outcomes in science lessons. Capuno et al. (2019) additionally emphasized that a

student's study habits and attitudes significantly impact their performance in school, including participation in extracurricular activities. Accordingly, students who participate in extracurricular activities occasionally miss class, affecting their performance thus, it should be monitored and considered.

In addition, one of the things that may contribute to poor learning outcomes is students' comprehension, especially when it comes to the usage of the English language. Cabural and Infantado (2023) found that students struggle to comprehend information in the content they are reading; hence is critical to address these prevailing concerns because these issues have a significant impact on students' academic achievement. Racca and Lasaten (2016) state that since English is the language of instruction for Science, Math, and English, students who have higher levels of English language proficiency also perform better academically in these fields. These findings corroborate the Philippines' poor performance in the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) in 2022 and the low results of the National Achievement Test (NAT) in the study's locale, where the overall mean percentage score was 32.26%, considered very low.

D. Students' Experiences after Exposure to (QTGT) in Relation to their Motivation

Theme 3. Team Dynamics and Peer Influence

Students shared their insights on how teamwork has influenced their learning experience. Many highlighted the positive effects of team activities, where tasks are effectively delegated among members. Students noticed a significant improvement in how teamwork is structured in their learning process.

They shared that, in previous group activities, they often relied only on the top performing students, leaving others disengaged. However, with QTGT, every member now takes responsibility and actively participates. *"The experience is better now, because before, even though we had teamwork, we relied too much on the top students. If others knew someone was good at science, they would just leave all the activities to them. But now it's different, my classmates work together. If someone doesn't understand something, others help out, and we support each other as a team..." "...If there's an activity, we now divide tasks among ourselves during teamwork."* This collaborative approach has not only improved teamwork but also facilitated better learning outcomes, as mentioned, *"If one teammate is struggling to understand, others would help," "Teamwork is great because we get to share ideas." "It's really nice because we learn much faster when we help each other."*

On the other hand, some students acknowledged the pressure within the team, wherein if they commit mistakes, it can affect the group's overall performance, so every member must study and prepare so they can contribute. *"I felt pressure from teammates. For example, if you're the one answering and you get it wrong, they get mad." ... "If you're struggling, you can always ask your classmates for help, but you shouldn't just rely on your team. You still need to study so you can contribute as well."* Despite this, students

appreciate the collaborative environment that has emerged, with several mentioning that teamwork makes learning easier and more enjoyable.

These claims are supported by Riyanti et al. (2024), who found that using Teams-Games-Tournament (TGT) learning significantly improved learning outcomes and motivation. Additionally, students' learning experiences can be enhanced when learning is complemented by collaborative learning (Chen & Lin, 2015). On the other hand, some students prefer to learn independently without the help of their peers. Saha and Morphew (2024) posit that students with greater academic competence may have less of a need for collaborative learning since they are more confident in how they learn.

Theme 4. Technology-Enhanced Learning and Accessibility

Students expressed a clear preference for using modern technology in their learning experience, particularly during tournaments. They emphasized how digital tools such as Quizizz and mobile devices have made the learning process more efficient and engaging compared to traditional paper-and-pen methods. One student noted that the availability of technology has simplified tournament processes, stating, *"It's better now because we have new tools. During the tournament, everything is much more accessible and easier."* The use of mobile phones during tournaments was seen as a major advantage. Participants highlighted that using digital tools made answering easier and more enjoyable.

Furthermore, the integration of technology helps to enhance their interest in learning. Compared to previous methods, which were more focused on solving and reporting, students now find the use of Quizizz combined with collaborative learning more enjoyable and motivating. As the student mentioned, *"Before, we would just solve problems and present the answers, but now we actively participate by answering questions, which makes learning more engaging and enjoyable."*

Overall, students acknowledged that technology-enhanced learning has contributed to a more engaging, efficient, and accessible learning experience. It enabled them to participate more actively, enjoy the learning process, and take advantage of modern tools to improve their academic performance.

The combined results of numerous studies highlight how interactive game-based learning systems, such as Quizizz, have a great deal of potential to increase student motivation and enhance academic performance (Maulidya et al., 2022). Through the use of interactive illustration, technology integration in the classroom has been demonstrated to increase student engagement, encourage active involvement, and make learning more fun (Raja & Nagasubramani, 2018).

Theme 5. The Role of Competition in Enhancing Students' Motivation

The responses from participants highlight the significant role that competition plays in motivating students during the Quizizz-based Team Games Tournament (QTGT). One of the aspects emphasized is the presence of a ranking system, which serves as an external motivator. Students are driven to perform better to avoid lower rankings,

enhancing a sense of self-improvement and accountability in their learning process. As the student stated, *"There's a ranking system. It encourages me to do better, like, 'I need to take this seriously because I don't want to rank low.'"*

Moreover, competition fosters enjoyment and determination, as another student expressed, *"For me, it was enjoyable because we learned something new. Plus, you don't want to lose, so you really want to be the one to answer. Even without help, you push yourself to get the correct answer."*

Teamwork has been shown as a critical factor in enhancing motivation. One participant highlighted the importance of collaborative effort in achieving success, stating, *"Teamwork is really great, ma'am, because we get to share ideas, especially when we want to be first or improve our grades. It really motivates us to work hard as a team."*

Additionally, the tournament's competitive nature introduces a challenging yet enjoyable learning experience, as expressed by several participants, *"the tournament is really fun because it pushes us to do our best." ... "The tournament is better because it's challenging and also its teamwork."*

The study of Kapoor and Anastasiu (2018) supports the idea that competitive active learning encourages active student participation and increased motivation, as seen by their use of the Competitive Learning Platform (CLP). The concept that competition can motivate students to participate more actively in their learning tasks, which provides automatic performance feedback. Likewise, Luarn and Chiu (2023) emphasized that teamwork and competition push students to strive for excellence, enable students to participate, and work effectively in groups, thereby enhancing their motivation.

Moreover, according to Yayla and Çevik (2022), some believe that competition in schools can be a powerful motivator, pushing students to do their best and helping them develop their skills and creativity. However, others argue that if not properly managed, competition can have negative consequences, such as increasing anxiety, fostering jealousy, and encouraging behaviors like cheating, all of which can damage students' self-esteem and relationships. Thus, maintaining a balance in competition is essential to ensure it fosters students' growth without compromising their well-being.

Conclusions

The results showed an improvement in learning outcomes between the two groups after exposure to QTGT, however, they remained below 75%, falling within the "Did Not Meet Expectation" level. This suggests that although the collaborative and gamified approach helped, it was not highly effective in enhancing students' cognitive learning outcomes.

In addition, the study found a significant improvement in students' motivation levels after exposure to QTGT. The QTGT group achieved a mean score of 3.63, or highly motivated, whereas the non-QTGT group scored 3.23, which remained in the moderately motivated level. The interactive, competitive, and team-based approach of the

intervention played an important role in enhancing students' motivation in learning science.

Moreover, the qualitative analysis highlighted students' meaningful experiences after exposure to QTGT. Accordingly, QTGT helped improve their understanding of the lessons through teamwork and peer collaboration. They appreciated the opportunity to share ideas, clarify misconceptions, and support other teammates, which created a more engaging and effective learning environment. The competitive aspect of QTGT also serves as a motivating factor since they want to excel and win during the tournament. However, factors such as class behavior, distractions, absenteeism, poor study habits, and difficulty understanding English may have contributed to students' low cognitive learning outcomes.

Recommendations

Educators may incorporate the Quizizz-based Team Games Tournament (QTGT) strategy in science instruction alongside review sessions and reinforcement activities to help students understand and retain knowledge over time. Teachers may also utilize collaborative learning by providing structured team roles and responsibilities to ensure the active participation of each member and enhance team learning. Incorporating competition in class may also increase motivation.

Parents may support their children's academic progress by encouraging regular class attendance and monitoring their performance. They may help minimize negative behaviors, reinforce good study habits, and create a structured learning environment at home. Additionally, they may set limits on mobile phone usage to reduce distractions and encourage students to focus on their studies.

Future research may use the findings of this study to further examine its effectiveness. Additionally, refining the QTGT implementation, such as integrating structured review sessions or modifying the framework to accommodate diverse learning styles, may enhance its effectiveness.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to ethical standards to protect the rights and well-being of all participants. Approval letters, consent, and assent forms were secured before the conduct of the study. Both participants and their parents were fully informed about the study's purpose and acknowledged that participation was voluntary, with the freedom to withdraw at any time. There were no conflicts of interest, and all findings were used solely for research purposes.

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